

The State of Cluster Development and Depth in the Global Innovation Index

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The indicator representing the state of cluster development and depth evaluates the level of development and the depth of innovation and industrial clusters within a specific region or country. Clusters are geographic concentrations of businesses, academic institutions, research entities, and related organizations that collaborate in specific sectors to promote innovation, competitiveness, and economic growth. This indicator examines a region's ability to create a collaborative and dynamic ecosystem where economic and institutional actors work together to leverage synergies and shared resources. The evaluation considers both the quantity and quality of these clusters, analyzing aspects such as the intensity of cooperation, the degree of sectoral specialization, and the capacity to generate new patents, technologies, or market innovations. A high score in this area indicates a well-structured environment capable of attracting investments, fostering the creation of skilled jobs, and supporting international competitiveness. The depth of clusters is particularly relevant as it reflects the efficiency and added value generated by interactions among the different stakeholders, significantly contributing to a country's technological and economic progress. The data refer to the period between 2013 and 2022.

The State of Cluster Development and Depth in the Global Innovation Index in 2022. The data on the state of cluster development and depth reveal significant diversity among countries in terms of their ability to create collaborative and supportive ecosystems for innovation. At the top of the rankings are the United States, with a score of 78.5, followed by China (72.6) and Switzerland (71.9), demonstrating a high level of maturity and complexity in their industrial and technological clusters. These countries benefit from highly developed economies, significant investments in research and development, and strong engagement between businesses, universities, and research institutions. Italy, with a score of 70.2, holds a respectable position, indicating a good level of cluster development. However, it is surpassed by countries like Switzerland and China, which demonstrate a greater capacity to harness systematic collaboration and innovation. Interestingly, Middle Eastern countries such as the United Arab Emirates and Egypt score similarly to Italy, reflecting growing attention toward the development of innovative clusters in the region. Below the 70-point threshold are advanced economies like Germany (68.5) and the Netherlands (68.5), which still exhibit strong innovative capacity. The inclusion of emerging countries like Indonesia (68.4) and Vietnam (65.1) among nations with competitive scores is noteworthy, highlighting the success of rapidly growing economies in building significant innovation ecosystems. More established Asian economies, such as Singapore (67.6) and Japan (64.4), known for their technological innovation, rank lower than expected. This may reflect differences in sectoral specialization or less emphasis on clusters compared to other development models. Similarly, Scandinavian countries like Sweden (64.9) and Norway (64.6), leaders in many other innovation indicators, do not excel in the specific ranking of cluster depth. Countries with transitioning or developing economies, such as Pakistan (56.1), Uzbekistan (59.9), and Tanzania (52.0), appear to be making efforts to improve their standing. However, they remain far from global leaders due to a lack of resources and sufficient infrastructure to build robust, interconnected clusters. At the bottom of the rankings are countries like Albania (28.9), Burkina Faso (28.7), and Angola (28.1), struggling to develop significant innovation clusters.

This can be attributed to limited access to capital, technological knowledge, infrastructure, and low levels of collaboration between local institutions and businesses.

The State of Cluster Development and Depth in the Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022.

The data reveal significant variation in the progress or decline of the development and depth of innovation clusters between 2013 and 2022. Some countries have experienced remarkable improvements, while others have faced notable declines, often influenced by economic, political, and social factors. Among the countries with the highest percentage improvement, Algeria stands out with an increase of 135.6% (from 20.5 to 48.3), followed by Egypt with a 69.2% rise (from 41.3 to 69.9). This progress indicates these countries' growing ability to develop collaborative ecosystems, attract investments, and integrate innovations into their economies. The increase could be attributed to government policies aimed at diversifying economies, investing in research infrastructure, and promoting collaboration between businesses and academic institutions. Emerging economies such as China (+21.6%) and Indonesia (+25.7%) have also shown improvements, consolidating their position as innovation hubs. China, in particular, has reinforced its global role, benefiting from massive investments in research and development and strong industrial policies. On the other hand, some countries have experienced significant declines. India saw a drop of 22.7%, with its score decreasing from 54.9 to 42.4. This may reflect structural challenges in integrating innovation policies, economic instability, or difficulties in creating synergies between economic sectors. Qatar also experienced a notable decline of 21.6%, falling from 69.9 to 54.8, possibly due to its reliance on traditional sectors such as oil and gas, which may have limited diversification and innovation. Significant declines are also observed in developed countries like the United Kingdom (-13.6%) and Finland (-13.9%), traditionally leaders in innovation. These declines might be linked to global economic challenges, shifts in public spending priorities, or reduced cooperation between economic and academic sectors. It is also noteworthy that Japan (-7.2%) recorded a decline despite its reputation for technological innovation, suggesting possible difficulties in regenerating its industrial clusters. The European Union shows a mixed performance: some countries, such as Italy (+13.2%) and Spain (+16.1%), improved their scores, indicating a recovery in support for innovation clusters, while others, like Croatia (-20.8%) and the United Kingdom, saw declines. This highlights the heterogeneity of innovation strategies among member states.

Conclusions. On average, the state of development and depth of clusters grew by 6.53% between 2013 and 2022. The top-performing countries are Algeria with +135.61%, Kyrgyz Republic with +76.52%, Egypt with +69.25%, Yemen with +58.37%, and Côte d'Ivoire with +54.74%. The worst-performing countries are Chile with -17.27%, Nicaragua with -19.37%, Croatia with -20.87%, Qatar with -21.60%, and India with -21.60%.

	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Algeria	20,5	48,3	27,8	135,61
	Kyrgyz Republic	23	40,6	17,6	76,52
	Egypt, Arab Rep.	41,3	69,9	28,6	69,25
	Yemen, Rep.	20,9	33,1	12,2	58,37
	Cote d'Ivoire	28,5	44,1	15,6	54,74
	Chile	55	45,5	-9,5	-17,27

Worse Performers	Nicaragua	38,2	30,8	-7,4	-19,37
	Croatia	41,2	32,6	-8,6	-20,87
	Qatar	69,9	54,8	-15,1	-21,60
	India	54,9	42,4	-12,5	-22,77

References

Arnone, M.; Legrande, A. (2024). The Green Trilemma: Energy Efficiency, Banking Stability and Climate Risk in the ESG Context at World Level.

Arnone, M.; Legrande, A. (2024). The People You Can Count on in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4873511.

Arnone, M.; Legrande, A. (2024). The Sustainability of the Factoring Chain in Europe in the Light of the Integration of ESG Factors. Available at SSRN 4880150.

Arnone, M., Angelillis, B., Costantiello, A., & Legrande, A. (2024). Graduates, Training and Employment Across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4850961.

Arnone, M., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Legrande, A. (2024). The Access to Credit in the Context of the ESG Framework at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4912994.

Arnone, M., Legrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2024). Banking Stability in the ESG Framework Across Italian Regions (No. 121452). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Costantiello, A., & Legrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. Discover Global Society, 2(1), 1.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Legrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In Data Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Legrande, A. (2024). Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4785815.

Legrande, A. (2024). Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions. Available at SSRN.

Legrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4772381.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Regular Internet Users Across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4782193.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771131.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771132.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Air Pollution in the ESG Model at the World Level. In *Intersecting Environmental Social Governance and AI for Business Sustainability* (pp. 93-122). IGI Global.

Magazzino, C., Madaleno, M., Waqas, M., & Leogrande, A. (2024). Exploring the determinants of methane emissions from a worldwide perspective using panel data and machine learning analyses. *Environmental Pollution*, 348, 123807.

Salvatore, D., Magazzino, C., Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2024). The economic determinants of world disorder events: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Policy Modeling*,